

A Study on Awareness and Usage of Internet Banking in Theni

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Abstract

The “Banking reforms” are directed towards improving the policy framework, financial health and the institutional framework. The Banking sector reforms measures to enhance efficiency and productivity through competition were initiated and sequenced to create an enabling environment for banks to overcome the external constraints from credit allocation to certain sector. The reforms measures have brought about sweeping changes in this critical sector of the Indian’s economy. Banking in India is generally fairly mature in terms of supply, product range and foreign banks. The major banking sector reforms comprises of modifying the policy frame work.

Keywords: Save time, Transaction easily, Technology improvement.

Introduction

Reforms in the financial sector, covering banking, insurance, financial markets, trade, taxation etc have been major catalyst in strengthening the fundamentals of the Indian economy. Reforms in the banking sector were introduced on the basis of the recommendations of different committees. Further, deregulation has opened up new opportunities for banks to increase revenues by diversifying into investment banking, insurance, credit cards, depositary services, financing, securitization etc. The “New Economic Policy” of structural adjustments and stabilization program was announced in June 1991.

History of Bank

Bank has developed during the British era. First bank was established by British East India Company. They have introduced three banks namely;

- Bank of Bengal in 1809,
- Bank of Bombay in 1840,
- Bank of Madras in 1843

These three banks were later amalgamated and is called Imperial bank. Then state Bank of India was taken over in 1955. The Reserve Bank of India was established in 1935. Banking sector reforms were an important part of the broader agenda of structural economic reforms introduced in India in 1991. The first stage of reforms was shaped by the recommendations of the committee on the financial system (Narasimham Committee) which submitted its report in December 1991.

Review of Literature

Sanchez and Gallie (2010) investigated the factors determining the usage of online banking in France. The authors compared the internet banking users of Mexican and French banks. They used the data of available Mexican study and survey analysis from 398 French bank users. The results of the survey revealed that there are six common factors affecting the usage of internet banking that are difficulty, compatibility, trust, third-party concerns and group influence.

Scope of the Study

The study is based on the awareness and usage of internet banking in Theni. This study covers a Internet Banking.

Objectives of the Study

For every work there should be an aim. Like that, this study has the following objectives:

- To know about the bank.
- To find out the profile of the sample respondents.
- To analysis the awareness and usage of internet banking in Theni.
- To offer the findings and suggestion of the study.

Data Collection

Both Primary and secondary data used in the present study.

Primary data: The data was collected through personal research in the form of questionnaire from 60 respondents.

Secondary data: Data was collected from various journals, books and magazines.

Tools for Analysis

- Percentage.
- Simple ranking.

Analysis and Interpretation

Socio Economic Status Of The Respondents

Table No. 1.1

Variables	Categories	No.of respondents	Percentage
Gender	Male	35	58.33
	Female	25	41.67
Age of the respondents			
Age	20-30 years	18	30
	30-40 years	22	36.67
	Above 40 years	20	33.33
Education qualification of the respondents			
Education qualification	SSLC	10	16.67
	HSC	12	20
	UG	30	50
	PG	8	13.33

Marital status of the respondents			
Marital status	Married	35	58.33
	Un married	25	41.67
Total		60	100

(Source: Primary data)

From the above table 1.1 interpret the majority of the respondents (58.33%) is under male, (36.67%) respondents are under age group of between 30-40 years; under educational qualification of the respondents, most of the respondents are (50%) having the qualification of UG degree and (58%) of the respondents are married.

Category of Bank

Table No. 1.2

S.No.	Types	Respondents	Percentage
1	ICICI	9	15
2	Indian Bank	15	25
3	TMB	10	16.67
4	SBI	20	33.33
5	Other Banks	6	10
Total		60	100

From the above Table No 1.2 interpret the majority of the respondents(33.33%) are using SBI bank. And (25%) respondents are using Indian bank.

Frequency of the Usage of Internet Banking

Table No. 1.3

Durations	Respondents	Percentage
Daily	20	33.33
Weekly	15	25
Monthly	11	18.33
Yearly	14	23.33
Total	60	100

Simple Ranking

Simple Ranking is used to verify that banking reforms performed by the customers.

Table No. 1.4

Save time	12	I
24 hours availability	11	II
Banking transaction is easy	9	IV
Transaction cost is cheap	10	III
Be technologically	7	V
Security	5	VII
Curiosity	6	VI

From the Table No. 1.4 it is observed that first rank was given to save time, second rank is provided to 24 hours availability, 3rdrank is provided to Transaction cost is cheap, 4th rank is provided to Banking transaction is easy, 5thrank is provided to Be technologically, 6th rank is provided to Curiosity, 7th rank is provided to Security.

Findings and Suggestions

Findings

This paper finds the usage of internet banking to know about the banking awareness to the people. The primary data collected from the 60 respondents regarding A Study on awareness and usage of internet banking.

- Of the 60 respondents selected for the study 35 respondents were male and 25 respondents were female.
- From these study 22 respondents belongs to the age group of 30-40 category.
- 30 respondents were having the education qualification of UG-degree.
- From 60 respondents, 35 respondents were married.
- From 60 respondents, 20 respondents Were using SBI.

Suggestion

From this above findings the researcher suggests the following points for the banking reforms to the customer.

Based on the research findings, it can identify the problem areas resulting in the lack of usage of internet banking in Theni. Hence, the banks need to improve the simplicity and operation convenience of banks online platforms. Further, the bank should educate the customers on how to operate internet banking on the internet.

Conclusion

The research findings revealed insights into the reasons that hinder the usage of internet banking services in Theni. The banks and policy makers have a major role to adopt in spreading knowledge of awareness about internet banking. Most of the customers have started to priority to prefer internet banking instead of traditional usage in Theni. According to customers internet banking is more effective than branch banking about time saving but still internet banking are improved.

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